

ORGANIZATION OF MOVEMENT SKILLS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN ON THE BASIS OF GAME

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ABSTRACT. This article describes the methods of organizing the motor skills of preschool children based on the means of mobile games. This research revealed the development of movement activity, physical qualities and movement skills of preschool children through movement games.

Key words: action games, children, action, skill, didactic, training

Literature Analysis and Methodology. Although some studies have focused on the targeted development of physical activity skills and mental processes in preschool children based on movement games, they have not been discussed in detail. In the process of achieving this goal, the organization of physical education and public health activities to develop children's motor skills in preschool institutions will provide a basis for solving the above problem. Updating the content, form, means and methods of the theoretical basis for the development of technology for the development of children's physical activity in the context of preschool education is carried out at the expense of the subject of the work. In the process of applying this subject, it is expedient to put forward the following hypothesis, including assumptions about the theoretical substantiation of the process of developing children's motor skills in the context of preschool education. The age characteristics of improving the physical fitness of preschool children have been identified, their development in the context of preschool education is based on theoretical and practical means, for which the following has been identified:

1. Age features of the development of physical qualities processes based on the use of movement games in the physical education of preschool children;
2. Laws on the relationship between the development of motor skills and physical qualities of preschool children;
3. Means and methods on the principle of influencing the physical qualities and development of motor skills of preschool children.

The practical and theoretical significance of the work is that the scientific data obtained in the course of research clarify the laws of the theory and methods of physical education in relation to the problems of improving the educational process in preschool institutions. Technology for the development of children's physical activity in the context of preschool education will be developed and theoretically substantiated. Features of the development of physical qualities in preschool children, mainly at birth, the child's blood is endowed with the appropriate set of physical capabilities placed by hereditary programs of special development.

Discussion and results. Action games are one of the main means of physical education of children. They can be used from an early age. During this period, children begin to acquire life skills such as running, jumping, throwing, climbing.

Preschoolers will be able to assess their movements and abilities as they compete in strength (arm pulling), agility (short-distance running, squats) and other qualities. In addition to physical development, movement games help to develop in children such qualities as will, courage, perseverance, endurance, courage. Children try to satisfy their great need for movement, usually through games. For them, play is, first of all, activity. During movement games, children's movements improve, they develop such qualities as initiative and independence, confidence and determination. Children first perform actions under the guidance of adults: for example, depicting a chicken or a bird - "threshing grain", "flying". In any independent play, children are not immediately able to show activity and initiative, their movements are uniform and limited. Examples of such games are "Take the flag", "Run to me", "Find the flag". It is necessary to follow a certain consistency in teaching games. For example, "Catch Me" is simpler than "Catch Me". In the first case, the child has to catch an adult, in the second game there is a risk of being caught, so the child has to use more physical force. Games need to be more diverse in content and include more complex tasks. Planning of experiments on physical education of preschool children was carried out on the basis of the scheme presented in Table 1. For five weeks, preschoolers consistently performed specially graded movement games for this purpose, which were combined with one or more of the five physical qualities to develop more strongly with one or more of the mental process indicators. Over a five-week period, children performed at least 12 movement games aimed at developing one of the five different physical qualities.

For example, the following tests were used to characterize endurance: running for 90 and 120 m for 5-year-olds; For 6-year-olds until the first stop and running for 120 m. This means that only one test was repeated for all age groups - running 120 m. Details on the use of this or that test are given below. Here are the materials of pedagogical experiments conducted in the educational institution No. 76 in Samarkand. The experimental and control group consisted of peers, 32 experimental lessons, 120 different movement games were used in the experiment. The planning of the pedagogical experiment was carried out as follows. Before starting the experiment, all children were tested to determine the initial state of development of physical qualities and mental processes.

Indicators of development of physical qualities of children aged 5-7 years

Tests			Experimental group			Control group				t
	M	±m	M	C	±m	M	C	C		
Power paw (right) kg	0'	4.9	0.3	1	33.0	5.82	0.26	0.94	20.6	1.2 P>0.05
Q	4.7	0.2	1.1	29	0.50	0.21	0.91	23.0	0.67>0.05	2.75 P<0.05
Paw (left) kg	0'	3.9	0.40	1.2	33.7	4.4	0.38	1.0	24.5	1.8 P>0.05
Long jump, m	0'	1.0	0.22	0.35	27.8	0.13	0.14	0.32	21.0	3.0 P<0.05
Q	0.8	0.0	0.18	19.1	0.93	0.04	0.14	16.3	3.3<0.05	3.15 P<0.05
Throwing	0'	1.5	0.15	0.38	16.95	2.52	0.19	0.43	13.6	3.75

the ball, m										P<0.05
Q	2.2	0.1	0.42	15.2	2.42	0.17	0.32	14.7	1.8<0.05	
Raise the legs at 10 s	Q	7.8	0.29	1.58	22.7	9.2	0.20	1.58	15.3	3,28 P<0,05
Endurance										
Running 70 m, s	0'	20	0.66	2.75	11.6	20.4	0.48	2.0	8.3	1,2 P>0,05
Q	2.0	0.5	1.48	7.6	18.0	0.38	2.3	7.7	3,1<0,05	
Running 120 m, s	0'	39	1,02	2,89	8,6	32,5	0,73	1,8	6,1	6,2 P<0,05
Q	39	0,4	2,16	9,2	36,2	0,47	1,9	5,8	3,7 R<0,05	
Speed										
Running out of place 70m, s	0'	2,22	0,13	0,34	9,7	2,71	0,19	0,5	9,6	1,9 P>0,05
Sit down, 10 times	0'	8,4	0,18	0,69	7,9	7,5	0,16	0,5	7,4	0,5 P<,05
Q	10	0,1	0,57	7,7	9,7	0,09	0,7	6,8	2,9 R<0,05	
Q	13,	0,1	0,85	8,4	12,1	0,08	0,6	5,7	3,8 R<0,05	

There were no significant differences in the initial values of children aged 5-7 years in the control and experimental group. Therefore, in further analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment, we only compare the final results. To examine the possibilities of power in the development of physical qualities in children during the experiment.

Experimental group on final control tests boys strength. According to all tests of readiness, they were far ahead of their peers in the control group. At the same time, as a result of pedagogical experience, the girls outperformed their peers in the control group by two out of four tests (Table 3). In all cases, the boys in the experimental group on the level of development of strength outperformed all their peers. The pedagogical experience of four-year-olds led to a significant increase in strength capabilities in both boys and girls compared to control groups. For example, in the experimental group, the absolute values of the strength of the right paw of the boys in the experimental group were 38.5%, and in the left paw - 44.2%. The results of the boys in the experimental long jump were 32% higher than in the control group, and 60% higher in the shot put. The strength of the right paw of the girls in the experimental group was 4.7% less than that of their peers in the control group, and 12% less in the left paw. However, in both cases, these changes were not obvious (Table 1).

Conclusion. In conclusion, the age-related features of the development of motor activity in preschool children were identified through experiments and theoretically substantiated. The use of movement games in physical education in preschool institutions helps to develop children's mobility, physical fitness, as well as improves the quality of their preparation for the transition to early school age.

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